

Predicting crop evapotranspiration and irrigation requirements with Machine Learning and satellite imagery.

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Adopting advisory systems that provide accurate forecasts of crop water requirements, specifically crop evapotranspiration, can enhance water use efficiency in agriculture. The successful development of these advisory systems relies on access to timely updates on crop canopy parameters (usually from satellite imagery) and weather forecasts several days in advance, at a low operational cost.

Common agronomy methods are relied upon for accurate estimations of reference evapotranspiration. Nevertheless, they require substantial and typically expensive data, as well as complex configurations, then hampering their integration into water management systems. Furthermore, these methods offer approximate estimations that are not usually aligned with real evapotranspiration measurements found in automatic weather stations. To address these issues, a Machine Learning (ML) model has been trained on in-field evapotranspiration measurements from real crops, and powered by a set of minimal weather forecast inputs.

An extensive experimental framework has been applied to our proposal and alternative methods. Target data comprises real evapotranspiration and weather forecasts from 100 real crops in Southern Spain spanning several years (2018-2021). Experiments have demonstrated the advantage of ML for evapotranspiration prediction when compared to state-of-the-art estimators, at the same time reducing input complexity.

1 Introduction

Optimal irrigation water management is one of the main challenges of precision agriculture and part of UN's development goals [1]. In this sense, automatized and intelligent water management systems could be especially helpful for open field crops where farmers must deal with the uncertainty of both climate conditions and water opportunity under climate change scenarios. Many world regions where open field irrigation is practiced during dry seasons are

characterized by negligible rainfall contributions (i.e.: Mediterranean crops).

Irrigation water requirements are essentially dominated by the estimation of **crop evapotranspiration** [2]. Crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) is determined using the concepts of crop coefficient and reference ET. Reference crop evapotranspiration, denoted as ET_o , represents the evapotranspiration from a well-watered reference hypothetical grass crop with specific characteristics. It can be estimated using mathematical models, such as the **Penman-Monteith** (PM) equation [2].

PM requires a wide set of inputs that reflect the evaporating demand of the atmosphere. However, input availability for PM (at reasonable costs) represents at the same time a prerequisite and a huge challenge for its adoption within operational advisory systems. The reward is still paramount as precise water estimation can help farmers in evaluating real water needs in crops and, therefore, in optimizing the irrigation scheduling.

Input factors in PM are mainly derived by Earth's weather conditions, and can be efficiently monitored using ground weather stations in real time. Nevertheless, farmers and irrigation system operators usually demands estimates of crop water requirements a few days later in advance of optimal irrigation scheduling. Thus, some more advanced advisory services proposed in the literature are based on **weather forecasts** produced by meteorological services, which implement Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models at different scales. NWP offers "Good, Cheap, and Fast" weather forecasts through service subscription, whose reliability has improved considerably in the 21st century [3].

On the other hand, some Earth Observation (EO) systems provide free multi-spectral images, which are exploited to recover **crop canopy** parameters that influence evapotranspiration processes. The evaluation of crop canopy parameters from multi-spectral images still represents an innovative and active research

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topic.

Simplified ET estimation methods based on satellite imagery and NWP could be a balanced alternative to canonical methods while relying on fewer variables [3]. **Hargreaves-Samani** (HS) follows this premise and provides ET_o estimations with fewer inputs, and then less sources of uncertainty. Its operational costs are also lower as the cost of advanced NWP outputs in operational mode is generally proportional to the number of required climate variables. In contrast, HS could also entail lower precision as its estimation is based on less information.

In this work, ML is intended to directly model relationships between input meteorological variables and real ET_o measured in crop fields. This model has been developed as a replacement to canonical methods (HS/PM) with the intention of improving their precision and lowering down their operating costs. Our proposal offers the following novelties:

- **Reduce the inputs** required by state-of-the-art reference evapotranspiration estimators by avoiding some complex variables involved in their formulations. Thus, reducing high implementation/maintenance costs of evapotranspiration estimation in water management systems.
- **Improve irrigation precision** by directly learning hidden relationships between meteorological variables and real ET_o .
- Introducing the **application of ML/AI** in the field of evapotranspiration forecasting for crop irrigation systems by leveraging open and reliable NWP forecasts, as well as free and high-resolution satellite imagery for canopy modeling.

This work has been generated as part of the MORERA project. This Spanish research project (funded by CDTI) is aimed at developing a personalized irrigation recommendation system for crop fields based on satellite imagery and Artificial Intelligence, as well as, a new generation of miniaturized and compact remote sensing instruments to respond with agility to users' needs.

2 Methods

The main objective of our irrigation prediction system is to provide a 5-days forecast of the cumulative water irrigation (CWI) requirements. A ML model has been designed to provide daily water estimation from time t (current time) to $t + n$ (from 1 to 5 days ahead) for each timestamp and crop field considered. CWI [2]

can be estimated using Equation 1, where ET_{max} represents the estimated maximum evapotranspiration and P_e the effective precipitation for a specific period.

$$CWI = ET_{max} - P_e \tag{1}$$

Although the previous formula implies several steps, the first and paramount part is the prediction of the maximum crop evapotranspiration (ET_{max}). This evapotranspiration refers to the state when water availability is sufficient for unhindered growth and development of a particular crop, measured in mm/day. The forecast of ET_{max} in several future steps is divided into two components, according to Equation 2.

$$ET_{max(t+n)} = K_c(t) \cdot ET_o(t+n) \tag{2}$$

First, synthetic crop coefficient (K_c) indicates the relationship between each specific crop and the reference evapotranspiration ET_o . K_c is computed once in time t using Sentinel-2 imagery and precipitation data [4]. In this work, K_c has been estimated from the synthetic crop coefficient methodology, which has been simplified and adapted to some study crops. This method is based on a linear relationship between K_c and a transpiration coefficient derived from the canopy spectral response and provided by ESA Sentinel-2 multi-spectral images. In our system, crop coefficient remains unaltered during the entire prediction period as we found it rarely varies in this short period (5 days). Thus, K_c remains as a factor independent to the ML modeling to simplify the model.

Secondly, ET_o component refers to the calculation of evapotranspiration from a theoretical reference surface. This theoretical value represents an imaginary grass reference crop, assuming a crop height of 0.12 m, a constant surface resistance of 70 s/m, and an albedo of 0.23 [2]. Unlike K_c , reference evapotranspiration fluctuates significantly given that it depends on uncertain climatic variables. Therefore, ET_o is deemed as a good candidate for ML modeling. Concretely, a regression model have been developed to predict ET_o using 3rd-party meteorological forecasts as inputs.

Input variables or attributes for the ET_o predictor corresponds with forecasts (from t to $t + 5$) for the following meteorological factors: air temperature, vapor pressure, net radiation, relative humidity, wind speed, and delta (prediction horizon in days). These weather forecasts are extracted directly from a NWP system, called NOAA GFS [5]. This service provides a meteorological prediction model produced by the National Centers for Environmental Prediction in the United States. The model covers the entire planet with a grid of points at a resolution of 28km between points. This data provider was selected for several reasons: free

Figure 1: Agro-climate stations network sourced by RIA. Data from all stations was collected for training and validating the model.

and easily accessible, high spatial and temporal resolution (every 6 hours), large historical database, constant updates (same source for inference and training), etc.

Real ET_o measurements (output variable) [6] originates from in-field evapotranspiration data collected from the Andalusian Institute of Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training (IFAPA, in Spanish). This data is sourced from the Agricultural Climatic Information Network of Andalusia (RIA, in Spanish), which was created to provide farmers and technicians with meteorological information for calculating crop water requirements and scheduling irrigation (see Figure 1).

The network of weather stations in RIA continuously supplies information about key meteorological variables, as well as, reference evapotranspiration data. This ET_o provider was selected for several reasons: based on real measurements instead of estimations, large historical data, extensive geographical coverage (Figure 1), easy and open access (via API).

Once the ML model forecasts reference evapotranspiration ($ET_{o(t+n)}$), the remaining factors in CWI (such as, K_c and P_e) are mathematically estimated using formulations designed by agronomy researchers [4].

3 Results

By combining both data sources (NOAA and IFAPA), a dataset has been generated by merging weather predictions with daily evapotranspiration for approximately 100 crop fields considering all available locations in Figure 1. In total, the number of records revolves around 5 million entries, with 7 numerical and continuous input variables and one output variable.

Two different regression models were evaluated for selecting the most accurate method. Both algorithms are based on decision trees given their low risk of

over-fitting and easy pre-processing. The first model is known as RandomForest [7] (RF). It is a combination of predictor trees, where each tree depends on the values of a randomly sampled vector, tested independently and with the same distribution for each tree.

The other model considered in our experiments is XGBoost [8]. It is based on the idea that multiple weak classifiers combined yields a robust classifier. Finally, two baseline methods were defined to demonstrate the utility of the ML approach. The first one (known as Naïve forecast) [9] set all forecasts to be the value of the last observation. The second baseline approximates evapotranspiration with the HS estimator, which is one of the SOTA techniques resorted by agriculture experts. Two evaluation metrics were assessed for this regression task: Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Squared Error (MSE), being MSE the loss function optimized by the two regressors.

Concerning validation in results, a hold-out scheme was used with special interest on avoiding data leakages from temporal and spatial components. From the entire set of locations, 90% of random ones were provided for training the algorithms, and only 10% were reserved for validation purposes. Similarly, from the entire set of months available, only the last two were isolated for validation.

After training, performance measurements were extracted for the different models and baselines. Preliminary results showed RF is less prone to over-fitting and yields more precise forecasts than XGBoost. Figure 2 evaluates if the best ML candidate outperforms the Naïve forecast based on the error metrics defined. This evaluation is bounded to 1-day ahead forecasts as they are the most accurate by definition for the Naïve baseline. For both metrics, RF's advantage is clear given that the baseline error is almost halved for MSE, and highly minimized for RMSE. Concretely, RF is able to achieve an average error (RMSE) of around 0.5 mm/day (approximately 15% error).

To certify the preference and benefit of our proposal, an additional evaluation has been performed by setting HS as baseline. For this assessment, the entire set of forecast horizons have been evaluated given that HS' inputs are available as forecasts for every horizon. Figure 3 illustrates outstanding advantage of our proposal when compared to HS (with several orders of magnitude). Beating both baselines reinforces the hypothesis that ML can yield more precise forecasts at a lower system cost compared to current SOTA approximations in the agronomic field.

Figure 2: Error metrics comparison (RMSE & MSE) for RF vs. Naïve forecast (1-day ahead)

Figure 3: Error metrics comparison (RMSE & MSE) for RF vs. Hargreaves-Samani (1-day to 5-day ahead)

4 Discussion

Modern precision agriculture requires optimizing water irrigation allocation and schedules to match the actual needs of crops. For that, accurate and cost-effective forecasts of crop water requirements with several days in advance are paramount. This is particularly important in irrigated regions like the Southern Mediterranean countries, where the main focus of forecasting crop water requirements is essentially predicting evapotranspiration.

Solid estimations for reference evapotranspiration are usually provided by well-established canonical methods, such as PM and HS. However, these methods demand a large set of information to operate, and hard configurations which could render as troublesome when integrated in modern water management systems. Even assuming HS simplifies estimations by only considering temperature and radiation factors, this approximate procedure is not always aligned with real evapotranspiration values sourced directly from climatic stations.

Known these problems, our approach aims at gaining frugality in inputs (reducing costs), and at the

same time, becoming a precise proxy to real evapotranspiration measurements as an alternative to other approximate methods. In our system, crop canopy parameters (K_c) are estimated without ML with ESA Sentinel-2 data using free multi-spectral images. Changes in crop parameters during this time period are deemed as minimal, so it can be assumed that up-to-date crop parameters remain unchanged for the forecast periods.

Contrary to K_c , reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) is strongly fluctuating and determined by weather factors, thus demanding a more dynamic approach based on learning. Our ML model is directly fed by NWP weather forecasts, which are well-known by its reliability, low-cost and high-availability. In particular, NOAA GFS is selected as our reference NWP provider for its outstanding features, such as: zero subscription cost, frequent update (6 hours), global coverage, among others. The key idea in our approach is to directly learn the relationships between weather forecasts affecting the crop, and the real evapotranspiration measurements associated to crop fields, differently from other approaches in the research. The previous hypothesis was deeply assessed on real ET_o values and weather forecasts spanning several years of data and collected from 100 crop fields.

The proposed approach has been validated in a thorough experimental framework that demonstrates its final validity for integration with intelligent water management systems. Subsequent results showed a simple but strong RF model capable of outperforming two meaningful and well-known baseline techniques: Naïve forecast, a classic baseline in time-series forecast hard to beat in most of problems [9]; and a SOTA estimator called HS known by its strong scientific background in agronomic. Preliminary experiments provide empirical validity to the solution, and supplies to the community with a novel solution for cost-effective and precise water irrigation prediction.

Our future plan is to extend experimentation to other geographical areas to assess the soundness of the proposal in other climate conditions and scenarios, as well as, different periods of time. Likewise, our intention is to explore more complex ML algorithms focused on time-series forecasting to improve the predictive performance without compromising the model's cost, such as LSTMs, Transformers, or other neural networks.

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References

1. Pereira, L. S., Oweis, T. & Zairi, A. Irrigation management under water scarcity. *Agricultural water management* **57**, 175–206 (2002).
2. Allen, R. G., Pereira, L. S., Raes, D., Smith, M., *et al.* Crop evapotranspiration-Guidelines for computing crop water requirements-FAO Irrigation and drainage paper 56. *Fao, Rome* **300**, D05109 (1998).
3. Pelosi, A., Villani, P., Falanga Bolognesi, S., Chirico, G. B. & D'Urso, G. Predicting crop evapotranspiration by integrating ground and remote sensors with air temperature forecasts. *Sensors* **20**, 1740 (2020).
4. Mateos, L., González-Dugo, M., Testi, L. & Villalobos, F. Monitoring evapotranspiration of irrigated crops using crop coefficients derived from time series of satellite images. I. Method validation. *Agricultural water management* **125**, 81–91 (2013).
5. NOAA. NOAA GFS numerical weather prediction model <https://www.nco.ncep.noaa.gov/pmb/products/gfs/>. 2024.
6. IFAPA. IFAPA RIA open data <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/agriculturaypesca/ifapa/riaweb/web/datosabiertos>. 2024.
7. Cutler, A., Cutler, D. R. & Stevens, J. R. Random forests. *Ensemble machine learning: Methods and applications*, 157–175 (2012).
8. Chen, T. & Guestrin, C. Xgboost: A scalable tree boosting system in *Proceedings of the 22nd acm sigkdd international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining* (2016), 785–794.
9. Hyndman, R. J. & Athanasopoulos, G. *Forecasting: principles and practice* (OTexts, 2018).